

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) 241202xt_2

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: 241202xt_2

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0057 Å Wavelength=1.54178

Cell: a=6.2772 (1) b=10.6974 (2) c=36.1669 (8)
 alpha=90 beta=90 gamma=90

Temperature: 296 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	2428.60 (8)	2428.60 (8)
Space group	P 21 21 21	P 21 21 21
Hall group	P 2ac 2ab	P 2ac 2ab
Moiety formula	C26 H25 F N2 O5	C26 H25 F N2 O5
Sum formula	C26 H25 F N2 O5	C26 H25 F N2 O5
Mr	464.48	464.48
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.270	1.270
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.777	0.777
F000	976.0	976.0
F000'	979.26	
h, k, lmax	7, 13, 44	7, 13, 44
Nref	4621 [2692]	4566
Tmin, Tmax	0.876, 0.962	0.522, 0.753
Tmin'	0.876	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.522 Tmax=0.753
AbsCorr = MULTI-SCAN

Data completeness= 1.70/0.99 Theta(max)= 70.210

R(reflections)= 0.0523 (3668)

wR2(reflections)=
0.1453 (4566)

S = 1.046

Npar= 311

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT220_ALERT_2_C NonSolvent Resd 1 C Ueq(max)/Ueq(min) Range 3.3 Ratio
PLAT242_ALERT_2_C Low 'MainMol' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of C10 Check
PLAT340_ALERT_3_C Low Bond Precision on C-C Bonds 0.00571 Ang.
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600 31 Report
0 2 0, 1 2 0, 1 1 1, 0 2 1, 1 0 2, 1 1 2,
1 0 3, 7 0 3, 0 1 4, 1 1 4, 1 1 5, 0 10 5,
1 0 6, 0 1 6, 1 0 7, 0 1 7, 1 1 7, 0 2 7,
0 0 8, 1 0 8, 0 1 9, 1 1 9, 0 0 10, 0 1 10,
1 1 10, 1 0 11, 0 9 26, 1 10 26, 1 0 28, 0 8 31,
0 7 34,
PLAT913_ALERT_3_C Missing # of Very Strong Reflections in FCF 22 Note
0 2 0, 1 1 1, 0 2 1, 1 0 2, 1 1 2, 0 0 4,
0 1 4, 1 1 4, 1 1 5, 1 0 6, 0 1 6, 0 1 7,
1 1 7, 0 2 7, 0 0 8, 1 0 8, 0 1 9, 1 1 9,
0 0 10, 0 1 10, 1 1 10, 1 0 11,

● **Alert level G**

PLAT003_ALERT_2_G Number of Uiso or U(i,j) Restrained non-H-Atoms 2 Report
PLAT177_ALERT_4_G The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains DELU Records 1 Report
PLAT192_ALERT_3_G A Non-default DELU Restraint Value for First Par 0.0010 Report
PLAT192_ALERT_3_G A Non-default DELU Restraint Value for SecondPar 0.0010 Report
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O1 . 103.9 Degree
PLAT791_ALERT_4_G Model has Chirality at C1 (Sohncke SpGr) R Verify
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G Number of Least-Squares Restraints 1 Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min). 4 Note
0 1 1, 0 0 2, 0 1 2, 0 0 4,
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 2 Note
PLAT916_ALERT_2_G Hooft y and Flack x Parameter Values Differ by . 0.12 Check
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G Number of HKL-OMIT Records in Embedded .res File 2 Note
0 0 2, 1 0 7,
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 1.914 Note
Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 7.59 or SHELX Weight 13.90
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 0 Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
5 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
13 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
7 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
7 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
3 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

